

INCLUSIVE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT AND ITS MAIN APPROACH IN
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Abstract. *This study provides information about modern methods of education based on an inclusive educational environment. It also discusses the relationship of education based on individual psychological and pedagogical approaches when working with students with disabilities. The relationship of inclusive education in mainstream education depends on pedagogical methods, and the relationship of students to the methods is studied.*

Keywords: *Inclusive education, pedagogical methods, psychological approaches, upbringing, pedagogical activity, psychological potential, educational program.*

INKLYUZIV TA'LIM MUHITI VA TA'LIMDAGI ASOSIY MUNOSABATI

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tadqiqotda inklyuziv ta'lim muhitiga asoslangan ta'limning zamonaviy metodlari haqida ma'lumotlar keltirib o'tilgan. Shuningdek imkoniyati cheklangan (nogironligi mavjud) o'quvchilar bilan ishlashda individual psixologik va pedagogik yondashuvlarga asoslangan holda ta'lim berish munosabatlari haqida aytib o'tilgan. Inklyuziv ta'limning asosiy ta'limdagi munosabati pedagogik metodlarga bog'liq bo'lib, o'quvchilarning metodlarga bo'lgan munosabati o'rganilib chiqilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Inklyuziv ta'lim, pedagogik metodlar, psixologik yondashuvlar, tarbiya, pedagogik faoliyat, psixologik salohiyat, ta'lim dasturi.*

Introduction

Inclusive education is the education of children with disabilities in schools together with their able-bodied peers. The goals and objectives of inclusive education are: - to create the necessary psychological, pedagogical, correctional conditions for the education of children and adolescents with disabilities in an educational organization, to implement general education programs and correctional work aimed at their capabilities, to ensure their spiritual development, social adaptation; to guarantee the right of students to equality in education; - to

meet the needs of disabled and able-bodied children with the active participation of society and the family; early adaptation to social life; - the educational process includes the pedagogical activity of the teacher and specially organized cognitive activity of students. At this point, let us focus on the analysis of these processes. The managerial role of a teacher in education, based on the social foundations of his profession, requires the mastery of the rich experience of his ancestors, the achievements of humanity in education over the centuries in the process of knowledge, labor communication, general relations, aesthetic and moral views. All this should be reflected in the implementation of the educational, educational, and developmental tasks of the teacher. Based on this, it can be said that in the educational process, the teacher teaches the students the knowledge that is at hand. In the educational process, he equips them with skills and qualifications. At the same time, he forms worldviews and moral norms in the students, forms interests and abilities, and increases their cognitive activity. The teacher's work opens up great opportunities for the purposeful formation of the student's personality. More precisely, he plans the entire educational process, organizes joint activities with the students in this process. He helps the students overcome difficulties and diagnoses their knowledge and the entire educational process. In turn, the students' work is directed to learning in the educational process, acquiring knowledge, skills and qualifications, and preparing themselves for useful activities for society. In the educational process, the activity of learners represents a multidirectional movement, and this movement greatly helps them in solving cognitive tasks. At preschool age, the conditions for educational activity are created, its individual elements are formed. In the process of classes at junior school age, it is necessary to form in children the goal of organizing their activities, to teach them to master various methods of activity. From the age of four, the child acquires a clear orientation towards the result. The teacher teaches children to listen, understand, perform the task, not to interfere with each other, supports immersion in the content of the lessons, encourages activity and aspiration. The goal of education depends on the pace and level of development of society, the requirements and capabilities of society, and the level of development and capabilities of pedagogical science and practice. The content of education depends on the social needs and goals of education, the pace of social and scientific and technical progress, the capabilities of children, the level of development of educational theory and practice, as well as the material, technical and economic capabilities of the educational institution. The quality (effectiveness) of education depends on the productivity of the previous stage and the results achieved in this stage, the nature and volume of the studied material, the organizational

and pedagogical impact on learners, and the children's learning abilities and time of education. The effectiveness of educational methods depends on the knowledge and skills in applying them, the purpose of education, the content of education, the age of learners, the opportunities for learning, material and technical support, and the organization of the educational process. The effectiveness of educational management depends on the intensity of feedback in the education system and the validity of corrections and influences. The effectiveness of educational stimulation depends on the internal incentives (causes) of education and external (social, economic, pedagogical) incentives. Inclusive education improves teaching methods and gradually introduces individualization principles into the educational process; - in the process of inclusive education, measures are taken to promote the spiritual and moral education of students, their physical and mental health and strength; - the number of specialized educational organizations for children with special educational needs is optimized, based on the physical and mental needs of students and the geographical location of educational organizations. The individual form of organizing children's educational activities reflects a number of positive aspects: the possibility of fully individualizing the content, method and pace of educational activities, the ability to track each student's actions and operations in solving a specific problem, etc. Inclusive education is an educational approach aimed at creating equal opportunities for all students and ensuring their individual development, taking into account the specific needs of each student. A variety of pedagogical methods and approaches are essential for the effective implementation of inclusive education. Inclusive education aims to provide equal opportunities in the educational process for all students with different social, economic, cultural, or physical abilities. The effectiveness of educational methods and techniques in inclusive education plays an important role in meeting the specific needs of students, increasing their interest in education, and ensuring success in the educational process. In our country, favorable conditions are being created for the education and upbringing of children with disabilities and their adaptation to social life. In order to integrate them into society and, first of all, restore their health as much as possible, work is being carried out on the basis of the "General Education Project for Children with Disabilities". This mainly involves using the opportunities of inclusive education. As a result, a deeper study of the pedagogical and psychological characteristics of organizing inclusive education, its specific capabilities, identifying problems associated with it, and substantiating aspects of its effectiveness is becoming an urgent scientific problem. Because the inclusive education method creates a favorable opportunity to ensure the full participation of all

children in the educational process, regardless of their mental and physical condition. A number of resolutions and regulatory documents have been adopted in Uzbekistan to develop inclusive education. These resolutions are aimed at ensuring the rights of children with disabilities to education, integrating them into mainstream schools, and meeting their special needs. Inclusive education is an educational system that aims to ensure equality in education, take into account the needs of each student and create the necessary conditions for their success. The methods and techniques used in inclusive education play an important role in organizing education in accordance with the individual needs of students. The use of effective methods has a positive effect on the academic, social and personal development of students, while making the educational process more effective. The methods and techniques used in inclusive education play an important role in achieving effective results by taking into account the different needs of students and adapting education. Differentiated teaching, multi-methodology, group work and individual approaches are effective tools for the successful implementation of inclusive education. The effectiveness of inclusive education has a direct impact on increasing students' academic success, social skills, and motivation.

Conclusion

The main principles of inclusive education are aimed at creating equal educational opportunities for all students, minimizing differences between them. In implementing these principles, the main goals are to take into account the individual needs of students, adapt the educational process and involve students in education. The inclusive education system embodies a number of important principles. These principles are based, first of all, on the recognition of the right of all children to equal education. The education system should create the same opportunities for children with disabilities, children with special needs, as well as all other students. In this system, the child will have the opportunity to receive education through special methods and approaches, depending on his abilities and needs. The second principle of the inclusive education system is the social integration of students. This principle is to teach students to study and learn together, to grow and develop as equal and respected citizens in society.

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